

Supplemental Material

Hindrances and Strengths in Software Delivery: Insights from a Developer Experience Study at the Swedish Transport Administration

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1 Full Questionnaire

Table 1 presents the full questionnaire used in **Hindrances and Strengths in Software Delivery: Insights from a Developer Experience Study at the Swedish Transport Administration**.

Table 1: Full Questionnaire

#	Question	Area	Answer type
1	How often do you need to perform ad-hoc tasks and/or put out fires?	Productivity	5-point Likert
2	How do ad-hoc tasks and/or firefighting affect your planned work?	Productivity	5-point Likert
3	How often do you need to do context switching during a day?	Productivity	5-point Likert
4	How do you experience the amount of planned work?	Productivity	5-point Likert
5	How do you experience your ability to manage your workload?	Productivity	5-point Likert
6	What are the biggest obstacles to your productivity?	Developer Experience	Free text
7	Which best practices in system development at the Swedish Transport Administration do you like the most? (Eg. working methods, methods, design patterns)	Developer Experience	Free text

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Full Questionnaire — continued

#	Question	Area	Answer type
8	How do you feel about the appreciation you receive for your efforts and achievements?	Culture	5-point Likert
9	My potential (competences and skills) is fully utilized in my daily work	Skills and competence	5-point Likert
10	I feel that as a team we consistently carry out the work we undertake to do	Culture	5-point Likert
11	New ideas are welcomed in my team	Culture	5-point Likert
12	Continuous improvement is part of our team's way of working	Culture	5-point Likert
13	We have a well-developed feedback culture in our team	Culture	5-point Likert
14	I feel that we have psychological safety in our team	Culture	5-point Likert
15	How often do you get help from your team when you need it?	Culture	5-point Likert
16	I feel that we are a team and not just a group of people	Culture	5-point Likert
17	I have the necessary tools in my daily work and workflows	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
18	I am satisfied with the tools and technology I use in my daily work	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
19	The team can easily deploy to production when needed	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
20	We use observability and telemetry in our team	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
21	We use test automation to replace manual testing	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
22	We use automation to replace manual production deployment	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
23	Security is consistently integrated into our development process	Developer Experience	5-point Likert
24	I continuously develop my knowledge and skills through my work	Skills and competence	5-point Likert
25	I have sufficient opportunities to develop my skills	Skills and competence	5-point Likert
26	I have an understanding of current trends and new technologies in my field	Skills and competence	5-point Likert
27	How often do I need to learn a new skill to perform my daily work?	Skills and competence	5-point Likert
28	How would you describe the level of difficulty of your work tasks?	Skills and competence	5-point Likert

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Full Questionnaire — continued

#	Question	Area	Answer type
29	I feel empowered to make decisions that are relevant to my role without needing constant approval from others	Responsibility and accountability	5-point Likert
30	I feel responsible for the outcome of my work, regardless of whether I succeed or not	Responsibility and accountability	5-point Likert
31	When mistakes are made, our team focuses on taking responsibility and learning rather than looking for scapegoats	Responsibility and accountability	5-point Likert
32	To what extent do you feel empowered to make decisions about how your work tasks should be performed?	Autonomy	5-point Likert
33	Our team has many dependencies on other development teams, which affects the speed and/or quality of our work	Autonomy	5-point Likert
34	How often does your team have to wait for approval or input from external stakeholders to continue with their tasks?	Autonomy	5-point Likert
35	What is your primary team?	Demographics	Free text
36	What is your secondary team?	Demographics	Free text
37	What project/product do you contribute primarily to?	Responsibility and accountability	Free text
38	What other projects/products do you contribute to?	Responsibility and accountability	Free text
39	Experience (years in current field)	Demographics	Free text
40	Your current role(s)	Demographics	Free text
41	I feel I have a good work-life balance	Culture	5-point Likert